

Co-funded by
the European Union

Knowledge & Creativity
European University

Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) Erasmus+

Nature, culture, landscape^{3rd} edition

Project Code: 2025-1-SK01-KA131-HED-
000312923-1

Nature, Culture, Landscape 3rd Edition | 2026

Organiser: Trnava University in Trnava

Online component: 11 & 18 February 2026

On-site component: 23–27 February 2026

Location: Trnava, Slovakia

Credits: 3 ECTS

Programme Focus & Activities

Ecocultural Heritage

Contemporary approaches to heritage integrating cultural, natural, and environmental dimensions.

Environmental Humanities & Landscape

Interdisciplinary perspectives on landscape, ecology, and human–environment relations.

Phenomenology of Place

Exploring space, body, movement, and lived experience.

Registration deadline:
23 January 2026

**FOR STUDENTS
AND STAFF**

👉 Scan to register

Field-Based Learning

On-site activities, guided walks, and experiential learning in museums and archaeological landscapes.

Collaborative Workshops

We use the latest technologies to figure out what's wrong with your health and diagnose medical issues.

In cooperation with the European University Alliance KreativEU (Knowledge & Creativity European University)

Trnava University – Faculty of Philosophy
Hornopotočná 23, 917 01 Trnava, Slovak Republic

lucia.novakova@truni.sk
michal.zvariketruni.sk

Co-funded by
the European Union

BLENDING INTENSIVE PROGRAMME (BIP) ERASMUS+

Nature, culture, landscape^{3rd} edition

Project Code: 2025-1-SK01-KA131-HED-000312923-1

Dates Virtual Component (online lecture)
11 & 18 February 2026
Physical Component (on-site)
23–27 February 2026, Trnava, Slovakia

Organizers

Trnava University in Trnava: Department of Philosophy, Department of Classical archaeology

Partner Institutions

- ✓ KreativEU (Knowledge & Creativity European University)
- ✓ University of Turin (Italy)
- ✓ Palacký University in Olomouc (Czech Republic)
- ✓ Jan Evangelista Purkyně University in Ústí nad Labem (Czech Republic)
- ✓ University of Hradec Králové (Czech Republic)
- ✓ Babeş-Bolyai University in Cluj-Napoca (Romania)

Objectives

The Blended Intensive Programme Nature, Culture, Landscape explores the intersections between ecological thinking, cultural practices, environmental humanities, and heritage studies. Through a combination of virtual and on-site activities, students examine how landscapes shape—and are shaped by—human meaning, memory, creativity, and ecological relations. The 2026 edition emphasizes ecocultural heritage, environmental philosophy, ancient eco-poetics, and phenomenological approaches to place, integrating theoretical and field-based components.

Teaching and Learning Methods

- ✓ keynote lectures
- ✓ discussions
- ✓ site-based learning
- ✓ workshops
- ✓ collaborative group work
- ✓ reflective assignments

Matěj Pudil

The Joyful Ecology

Veronika Konrádová (online)

Ancient Eco-poetics: Mythical Landscapes in Homer and Plato

Cristina Vendra

The Social Imaginary as an Intertwined Concept: Hermeneutics and Cultural Anthropology

Ion Copoeru (online)

The Good Shepherd: The Ecology of Skills in Pastoral Life

Radu Mârza (online)

The Railway Landscape (1830-1930)

Jan Halák

Phenomenology of Space: Place, Body, Movement

Paolo Furia

The Sacred Mountain: Transcultural Perspectives on Ecophenomenological Limits

Michal Zvarík

Spectral Phenomenology and Landscape

Lucia Nováková

Ecocultural Heritage: Contemporary Paradigms and Approaches

Jaroslava Vydrová

Searching for a home. The human being and its place in the world

Zuzana Jarůšková

Sacred Bronze Age Landscape: Exhibition Practices

Recognition

Course code: **XKam102 Natura et Cultura**
Credits awarded: **3 ECTS**

Trnava University – Faculty of Philosophy
Hornopotočná 23, 917 01 Trnava, Slovak Republic

lucia.novakova@truni.sk
michal.zvarik@truni.sk

Co-funded by
the European Union

PROGRAMME

 Online component:
11 & 18 February 2026

The Good Shepherd: The Ecology of Skills in Pastoral Life – *Ion Copoeru*

The Railway Landscape (1830–1930) – *Radu Mârza*

 On-site component:
23–27 February 2026

 Location: **Tnava, Slovakia**

Nature, Culture, Landscape 3rd Edition | 2026

**TRNAVA
UNIVERSITY –
RECTORATE**

**23 Monday
FEBRUARY
2026**

- ✓ **The Joyful Ecology** – *Matěj Pudil*
Ecocultural Heritage: Contemporary Paradigms and Approaches – *Lucia Nováková*
- ✓ **Curator-led tour (Ján Koniarek Gallery)**
- ✓ **Panel Session I** – *Paolo Furia · Adrián Kobetič · Lucia Nováková* (Moderator: *Jaroslava Vydrová*)
Dinner provided by the organisers

**WESTERN
SLOVAKIA
MUSEUM,
TRNAVA**

**24 Tuesday
FEBRUARY
2026**

- ✓ **The Sacred Mountain: Transcultural Perspectives on Ecophenomenological Limits** – *Paolo Furia*
- ✓ **Phenomenology of Space: Place, Body, Movement** – *Jan Halák*
- ✓ **Panel Session II** – *Matěj Pudil · Jan Halák · Andrej Sabov* (Moderator: *Michal Zvarík*)
- ✓ **Guided Museum Walk: Landscape Narratives in Exhibitions** – *Andrej Sabov, Matej Krnáč*
Dinner provided by the organisers

**MALÝ BERLÍN
(CULTURAL
CENTRE),
TRNAVA**

**25 Wednesday
FEBRUARY
2026**

- ✓ **University Campus Walk** – *Henrieta Žažová*
- ✓ **Ancient Eco-poetics: Mythical Landscapes in Homer and Plato** – *Veronika Konrádová* (online)
- ✓ **The Place and the Environment of Human Being** – *Jaroslava Vydrová*
- ✓ **World Café: Collaborative Discussions** – Moderated group work
- ✓ **Guided tour of the Synagogue**
Dinner provided by the organisers

**ARCHAEOPA
RK CÍFER–
PÁC**

**26 Thursday
FEBRUARY
2026**

- ✓ **Roman-Style Cooking Workshop & Shared Lunch**
- ✓ **Site Introduction & Guided Walk** – *Daniel Dida, Lucia Nováková*
- ✓ **The Social Imaginary as an Intertwined Concept: Hermeneutics and Cultural Anthropology** – *Cristina Vendra*
- ✓ **Sacred Bronze Age Landscape: Exhibition Practices** – *Zuzana Jarůšková*

**TRNAVA
UNIVERSITY
– AULA
PAZMANEUM**

**27 Friday
FEBRUARY
2026**

- ✓ **Spectral Phenomenology and Landscape** – *Michal Zvarík*
- ✓ **Wrap-up Session & Certificate Distribution**

17 Online Wednesday | 11 February 2026

16:30 – 17:00 (CET)	Q&A Session	Organizers	Online - Link
17:00 – 18:00 (CET)	Lecture: <i>The Good Shepherd: The Ecology of Skills in Pastoral Life</i>	Ion Copoeru (Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca)	

17 Online Wednesday | 18 February 2026

17:00 – 18:00 (CET)	Lecture: <i>The Railway Landscape (1830–1930)</i>	Radu Mârza (Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca)	Online - Link
------------------------	---	---	-------------------------------

📍 On-site Monday | 23 February 2026 | Trnava University, Jan Koniarek Gallery

13:00 – 13:30	Registration, coffee, group photo		Trnava University – Rectorate meeting room
13:30 – 13:40	Welcome & Opening of the BIP	Programme coordinators, Trnava University	Trnava University – Rectorate meeting room
13:40 – 14:40	Lecture: <i>The Joyful Ecology</i>	Matěj Pudil	Trnava University – Rectorate meeting room
14:40 – 15:40	Lecture: <i>Ecocultural Heritage: Contemporary Paradigms and Approaches</i>	Lucia Nováková	Trnava University – Rectorate meeting room
16:00 – 16:45	Curator-led tour	Adrián Kobetič	Ján Koniarek Gallery.
16:45 – 17:45	Panel Session I	Paolo Furia · Adrián Kobetič · Lucia Nováková · Moderator: Jaroslava Vydrová	Ján Koniarek Gallery: Library
18:00 – 20:00	Dinner		Trnava

📍 On-site Tuesday | 24 February 2026 | Western Slovakia Museum

10:00 – 11:00	Lecture: <i>The Sacred Mountain: Transcultural Perspectives on Ecophenomenological Limits</i>	Paolo Furia	Western Slovakia Museum
11:00 – 12:00	Lecture: <i>Phenomenology of Space: Place, Body, Movement</i>	Jan Halák	Western Slovakia Museum
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch break (individual arrangements, at own expense)		Trnava
13:30 – 14:30	Panel Session II	Matěj Pudil · Jan Halák · Andrej Sabov · Moderator: Michal Zvarík	Western Slovakia Museum

15:00 – 16:00	Guided museum walk: landscape narratives in exhibitions	Andrej Sabov · Matej Krnáč	Western Slovakia Museum
18:00	Dinner		Trnava
📍 On-site Wednesday 25 February 2026 Malý Berlin Cultural Centre, Synagogue			
10:00 – 12:00	University Campus Walk	Henrieta Žažová	Trnava
12:00 – 12:45	Lunch & Coffee		Trnava University (Canteen)
13:00 – 14:00	Lecture: <i>Ancient Eco-poetics: Mythical Landscapes in Homer and Plato</i>	Veronika Konrádová (online)	Malý Berlín, Trnava
14:00 – 15:00	Lecture: <i>The Place and the Environment of Human Being</i>	Jaroslava Vydrová	Malý Berlín, Trnava
15:00 – 16:30	World Café	Moderated group work	Malý Berlín, Trnava
16:45 – 17:45	Guided tour		Synagogue – Centre for Contemporary Art
18:00	Dinner		Trnava
📍 On-site Thursday 26 February 2026 Archaeopark Cífer - Pác			
9:30	Departure from Trnava		Trnava
10:00 – 12:00	Roman-Style Cooking Workshop + Lunch		Archaeopark Cífer-Pác
12:30 – 13:30	Site introduction & guided walk	Daniel Dida · Lucia Nováková	Archaeopark Cífer-Pác
13:30 – 14:30	Lecture: <i>The Social Imaginary as an Intertwined Concept: Hermeneutics and Cultural Anthropology</i>	Cristina Vendra	Archaeopark Cífer-Pác
14:30 – 15:00	Lecture: <i>Sacred Bronze Age Landscape: Exhibition Practices</i>	Zuzana Jarůšková	Archaeopark Cífer-Pác
16:00	Return to Trnava - free time		Trnava
📍 On-site Friday 27 February 2026 Trnava University			
09:30 – 10:30	Lecture: <i>Spectral Phenomenology and Landscape</i>	Michal Zvarík	Trnava University – Aula Pazmaneum
10:30 – 11:00	Wrap-up session, certificate distribution, group photo - end of programme		Trnava University – Aula Pazmaneum

Getting to Trnava

Trnava is located in western Slovakia, approximately 50 km from Bratislava and 130 km from Vienna. The city is easily accessible by train, bus, or car.

Airports

Bratislava Airport (BTS – M. R. Štefánik Airport) – 45 km (~35 min by car)

Taxi: €50–60 to Trnava

Public transport: Bus No. 61 → Bratislava Main Train Station (Hlavná stanica) → direct train to Trnava (~30 min)

Ride-hailing: Bolt, Uber (availability may vary)

Vienna International Airport (VIE) – 130 km (~1 h 40 min by car)

Direct bus: FlixBus or Slovak Lines to Bratislava (~1 h 15 min) → train/bus to Trnava

Private transfer/taxi: ~€120–150

Train: S-Bahn to Vienna Main Station → Railjet to Bratislava → connecting train to Trnava

By train

Frequent connections from Bratislava Main Train Station (Hlavná stanica) (~30 min)

Timetable: www.zssk.sk

By bus:

Bratislava Nivy Bus Station → Trnava Bus Station (~45 min)

Timetable: www.cp.sk

Local transport in Trnava

Most hotels and venues are within walking distance of Trnava University

Taxi services: Profi TAXI (+421 33 16444), Team Taxi (+421 940 747 474), Alpha Taxi (+421 901 711 711), Yellow Taxi (+421 33 3030 303), Taxi Smart (+421 908 939 393), Color Taxi (+421 948 252 525), Euro Taxi TT (+421 911 655 882)

Ride-hailing: Bolt – Trnava

Nature, Culture, Landscape 3rd Edition | 2026

Co-funded by
the European Union

FEBRUARY 23–27, 2026

**TRNAVA UNIVERSITY
IN TRNAVA**

Hornopotočná 23,
91701 Trnava

truni.sk

